

Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: PantaRhei: Gas flows in galaxies at Cosmic Noon

Creator: Alice Concas

Principal Investigator: Alice Concas

Data Manager: Alice Concas

Affiliation: Scuola Normale Superiore

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3203-9818

Project abstract:

The formation and evolution of galaxies over cosmic time is driven by the continuous flow of gas in and out of the system, the so-called "**galaxy baryon cycle**". Current theoretical models suggest that feedback from star formation (SF) and active galactic nuclei (AGN) leads to gas outflows, regulating SF activity and enriching the metal content of galaxies. This ejective feedback is thought to be particularly powerful at $z=1-2$, during the peak of SF and AGN activity, an epoch known as Cosmic Noon. Yet, a comprehensive understanding of gas outflows at $z=1-2$ remains elusive. The PantaRhei project hosted at SNS seeks to fully characterise the galaxy baryon cycle at Cosmic Noon using a unique approach: (i) build the largest, high-resolution ($R>3000$), optical-restframe spectroscopic sample to date by combining new data from Subaru/FMOS (with exclusive access) and public archival data from VLT/KMOS, totaling ~ 7600 galaxies at $z=1-2$; (ii) gather direct evidence of ionized gas outflows through the study of emission lines, employing stacking and modelling techniques that I have pioneered during the past years; (iii) explore archaeological evidence of multiphase gas outflows using the footprints left in the chemical enrichment of gas and stars; and (iv) build mock optical-restframe spectra from zoom-in simulations using the theoretical prescriptions developed at the Host Institute. This approach will allow quantifying the impact of ionized gas outflows on the overall gas phase and determine whether these outflows are transient or enduring features in galaxy life cycles. Comparing these observational findings with predictions from cosmological hydrodynamical simulations of galaxy formation will provide crucial constraints for refining numerical models of SF and AGN feedback. This project will advance our understanding of galaxy formation and guide the planning of future surveys with instruments like JWST/NIRSpec, VLT/MOONS, VISTA/4MOST, and ELT.

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PantaRhei: Gas flows in galaxies at Cosmic Noon

Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

Yes, the PantaRhei project will use existing data to quantifying the impact of ionized gas outflows on the overall gas phase and determine whether these outflows are transient or enduring features in galaxy life cycles. In the following table I will provide the specifics of each DATASET.

Dataset name/ Code package name	Dataset description / Code package description	File format	Volume/size	Data standard used	Metadata standard used	Storage location	Access conditions	Reuse conditions
Statistical galaxy sample and catalogue	<p>I will create a unique sample of more than ~7600 galaxies, covering 4 dex in stellar mass, $\text{LOG}(M_{\text{star}}/M_{\text{sun}}) = [8-12]$, and $\text{SFR} = [0.1-1000] M_{\text{sun}}/\text{yr}$, by combining (1) new sensitive near-IR high-resolution spectra of 5484 galaxies from the Fiber Multi Object Spectrograph (FMOS)-COSMOS survey, with (2) ~2300 IFS observations from the K-band Multi-Object Spectrograph (KMOS) at the VLT obtained by KLEVER, KMOS3D, KROSS, KGES, KASHz, KLASS, KLENS and KURVS surveys. The combinations of these data-sets will provide the largest, high-resolution ($R > 3000$), optical rest-frame spectroscopic galaxy sample to date. All FMOS and KMOS data have recently become publicly available. For each galaxy spectrum I will associate the archival multi-wavelength photometry and derived physical quantities such as stellar masses, SFR, AGN activity, and global structural parameters (e.g. size and inclinations). This DATASET will be used to reach the objectives number 1 (provide a statistical/direct evidence of outflows at cosmic noon) and number 3 (provide an archeological evidence of gas outflows imprinted on the chemical enrichment of galaxies)</p>	<p>One-dimensional galaxy spectra will be stored in FITS format following standard spectral conventions (wavelength, flux, error arrays). Derived catalogues containing photometry, stellar mass, star-formation rate (SFR), AGN activity, galaxy sizes and inclinations will be provided in FITS tables for accessibility.</p>	<p>The expected size for the spectra and catalogue is around 10 GB.</p>	<p>Physical quantities will use standard astronomical units (e.g. Å or nm for wavelength, $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{Å}^{-1}$ for flux, magnitudes in AB system, stellar mass in M_{sun}, SFR in $M_{\text{sun}}/\text{yr}^{-1}$). Coordinates will be given in ICRS (J2000), and dates will follow ISO 8601 format. Object classifications (e.g. AGN, star-forming) will follow commonly used astronomical definitions.</p>	<p>Metadata will follow FITS header conventions and IVOA (International Virtual Observatory Alliance) standards, including standard keywords for wavelength calibration, units and redshift. Catalogue metadata will include clear column descriptions, units, and provenance.</p>	<p>All data are accessed at project start from public repositories: the FMOS-COSMOS survey website and the ESO Science Archive Facility. Specifically, the FMOS-COSMOS survey (Kashino et al. 2019, <i>ApJ</i>, 241, 10) will be accessed directly from the FMOS-COSMOS public data repository: https://member.ipmu.jp/fmos-cosmos/FC_catalogs.html. The KMOS observations from the KLEVER, KMOS3D, KROSS, KGES, KASHz, KLASS, KLENS, and KURVS surveys will be accessed from the ESO Science Archive Facility, via the KMOS data collection portal: https://archive.eso.org/scienceportal/home?data_collection=KMOS. All datasets are publicly accessible, fully reduced, and accompanied by standard metadata and calibration information. No proprietary or restricted-access data are used at any stage of the project.</p>	<p>All data generated by the project will be made openly available after publication or project completion, without access restrictions. Data will be released in standard formats via trusted repositories with persistent identifiers.</p>	<p>Reuse of FMOS-COSMOS and ESO/KMOS data follows the original providers' citation requirements. All data generated by the project will be released under a CC BY 4.0 license, and software under an open-source license, in compliance with Horizon Europe and MSCA open science policies.</p>

Mock galaxy spectra	I will use existing high-resolution zoom-in simulations (from SERRA zoom-in cosmological simulations) to generate synthetic near-IR spectroscopic observations matching the observational properties (resolution, line spread function, pixel size, disc inclination and noise levels) of the KMOS and FMOS dataset described above. This DATASET will be used to reach the objectives number 2 (provide a quantitative comparison of simulated and observed gas outflows).	As done for the observed galaxy spectra dataset, the mock one-dimensional galaxy spectra will be stored in FITS format following standard spectral conventions (wavelength, flux, error arrays). Derived catalogues containing photometry, stellar mass, star-formation rate (SFR), AGN activity, and galaxy sizes will be provided in FITS tables for accessibility.	The expected size for the mock spectra and catalogue is around 10 GB.	Physical quantities will use standard astronomical units (e.g. Å or nm for wavelength, $\text{erg s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{Å}^{-1}$ for flux, magnitudes in AB system, stellar mass in M_{sun} , SFR in $M_{\text{sun}}/\text{yr}^{-1}$). Coordinates will be given in ICRS (J2000) , and dates will follow ISO 8601 format. Object classifications (e.g. AGN, star-forming) will follow commonly used astronomical definitions.	Metadata will follow FITS header conventions and IVOA (International Virtual Observatory Alliance) standards, including standard keywords for wavelength calibration, units and redshift. Catalogue metadata will include clear column descriptions, units, and provenance.	All mock spectra and associated physical quantities will be generated from the high-resolution simulations of high-z galaxies generated with the SERRA zoom-in simulations (Pallottini A., et al., 2022, MNRAS 513, 5621). We will run SERRA simulations up to $z=1-2$ and produce KMOS and FMOS like observations. We will use CLOUDY public code (Ferland G. J. et al., 2017, Rev. Mex. Astron. Astrofis., 53, 385) to compute the line emission of interest.	All data generated by the project will be made openly available after publication or project completion, without access restrictions. Data will be released in standard formats via trusted repositories with persistent identifiers.	All mock data generated by the project will be released under a CC BY 4.0 license in compliance with Horizon Europe and MSCA open science policies.
DISC-O code	I will provide a python version of the Disc-Outflow decomposition (DISC-O) software used to decouple line broadening between virial motions and outflow in galaxy spectra. Specifically, I will use the innovative technique I developed and successfully tested on KLEVER data (Concas A., et al., 2022, MNRAS 513, 2535). This consists of (i) building, for each galaxy, mock observations of rotating disks using the public available KINMS code (Davies et al. 2013 MNRAS 429, 534-555) taking into account all the characteristics of the observational sample, (ii) generate a mock stacked spectrum obtaining the expected line shape from purely virial motions, and (iii) compare that with the observed stacked spectrum to search for perturbed kinematics due to outflowing material (Concas A., et al., 2022, MNRAS 513, 2535). This DATASET will be used to reach the objectives number 1 and 2.	All software developed within the project will be written in Python and stored as plain-text source files (.py). Configuration and environment files will be provided in standard open formats such as requirements.txt, pyproject.toml, and .yaml. Documentation will be provided in Markdown format (README.md).	The total size of the software repository is expected to remain below 100 MB, including source code, configuration files, and documentation. No large data products will be stored in the code repository; all scientific datasets will be accessed externally from established astronomical archives.	The code will follow established community standards for scientific Python software, including: (i) PEP 8 for code style and formatting; (ii) PEP 257 for docstrings and in-code documentation; (iii) Git for version control, reproducible software environments defined via requirements.txt. Use of widely adopted scientific libraries (e.g. NumPy, SciPy, Astropy) that implement standard astronomical conventions.	Software metadata will be provided through: (1) A comprehensive README.md describing the purpose of the code, installation, dependencies, and usage examples. (2) Inline docstrings documenting functions, classes, and workflows. (3) A CITATION.cff file specifying authorship, version, license, and preferred citation. (4) Versioned releases and changelogs maintained through GitHub tags and release notes. This metadata will support findability, citability, and reuse , in accordance with FAIR principles for research software.	During development, the code will be stored in a private GitHub repository , ensuring version control, change tracking, and secure access for project members. Upon publication of scientific results or at the end of the project, stable releases of the code will be made publicly available on GitHub . Long-term preservation will be ensured by archiving each public release in Zenodo , which will automatically assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) . The Zenodo record will be linked to the corresponding GitHub repository and release.	All software developed within the project will be made openly accessible . The code will be released on GitHub under an open-source license (e.g. MIT). Archived versions hosted on Zenodo will be accessible without restrictions and citable via a DOI. Access will be granted immediately upon public release, with no embargo period. No ethical, legal, or commercial limitations apply, as the software does not include personal or sensitive data.	The project will rely on widely used, open-source Python libraries (e.g. NumPy, SciPy, Astropy, Matplotlib) and the open access KINMS code (Davies et al. 2013 MNRAS 429, 534-555). These libraries are released under permissive open-source licenses (e.g. BSD or MIT), which allow reuse, modification, and redistribution. All reused software will be cited appropriately in documentation and publications, in accordance with their respective licensing and citation guidelines.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

See table above.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

See table above.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

See table above.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

See table above.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The dataset described above will be valuable to both observational astronomers and theoretical researchers. Observers may use it to compare independent evidence of gas outflows identified with different techniques, or to apply and test the DISC-O outflow decomposition method. Theorists may use the dataset to compare predictions from simulations that implement different models of ejective feedback. In addition, these datasets can support the planning of future observational campaigns with next-generation facilities, such as MOONS, 4MOST, and ELT spectrographs.

FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

All data generated within the project will be made findable through the use of persistent identifiers and rich metadata (see the table above), in accordance with the FAIR principles and the Horizon Europe Open Research Data policy.

Final data products, including value-added galaxy catalogues and derived spectra, will be deposited in trusted, community-recognized repositories that assign persistent identifiers (DOIs). These identifiers will be referenced in all related publications and documentation to ensure long-term discoverability.

Comprehensive metadata will accompany each dataset, including a detailed description of the data content, file formats, units, calibration procedures, provenance, and versioning. Metadata will follow established astronomical standards and will be provided in both human- and machine-readable form.

Software releases will also be assigned persistent identifiers via DOI-minting repositories, ensuring that both data and code are uniquely identifiable, citable, and traceable over time.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

See above

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes. Descriptive, standardized search keywords will be included in the metadata to maximize discoverability and reuse, following community conventions and FAIR principles.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes. Metadata will be deposited in Zenodo and CDS (Centre de Données astronomiques de Strasbourg) using machine-readable standard formats, enabling automated harvesting and indexing by discovery services

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes. Project data will be deposited in trusted repositories, specifically Zenodo and CDS, ensuring long-term accessibility and compliance with MSCA open science requirements.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Yes. Deposition requirements and workflows for Zenodo and CDS have been reviewed and are compatible with the project's data formats and metadata.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes. Zenodo and CDS assign DOIs to deposited datasets, which resolve to a digital landing page containing the data, metadata, and documentation, ensuring persistent access and citability.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

All project data will be openly available via Zenodo and CDS, with no legal, contractual, or ethical restrictions. Open access will be ensured immediately after validation or publication in compliance with MSCA and Horizon Europe open science policies.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The data will be made available as soon as possible after the completion of the project. Specifically, the "Statistical galaxy sample and catalogue" and "Mock galaxy spectra" datasets will be first used for the project WP1, WP3 and WP2, respectively. After the publication of the results concerning WP1,2, and 3 all data will be deposited in Zenodo and CDS, ensuring open access in line with MSCA and Horizon Europe policies.

Initially, data, software, algorithms, and documentation ("DISC-O" code) will be accessible exclusively to internal collaborators via the existing Cosmology Group web page (to allow quality control and publication), with public access scheduled for the project's conclusion.

This will ensure effectiveness, transparency and reproducibility of our work, fostering a broader and more diverse engagement with our observed and synthetic data, as well as the methodology we adopt.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes. Project data will be freely accessible via standard protocols: HTTP/HTTPS and API for Zenodo, and VizieR/TAP/VO interfaces for CDS, ensuring machine- and human-readable access.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No permanent restrictions are planned. Any temporary embargo (only before the publication results) will restrict access to project members on secure servers. Afterward, all data will be openly accessible via Zenodo and CDS, using standard protocols.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Public access via Zenodo and CDS does not require authentication; therefore, user identity will not be tracked. During temporary embargoes (only before the publication results), access on institutional servers will be restricted to authorized project members.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

No, there is no need for a data access committee for this project.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes. Metadata will be openly available under CC0, include all information needed to access and interpret the data, follow DataCite/Dublin Core and IVOA standards, and be deposited in Zenodo and CDS

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Yes. All metadata will be openly available under a CC0 license, and will include persistent identifiers, descriptions, file formats, keywords, and access information to enable discovery and reuse via Zenodo and CDS

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes. Metadata will include documentation and references to required software, and project-developed analysis code will be released as open-source via GitHub and Zenodo, ensuring data are fully interpretable and reusable.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and reuse within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Data and metadata will follow community standards: FITS and CSV formats, IVOA-compliant FITS headers, DataCite/Dublin Core metadata, controlled vocabularies for classifications and units, and consistent naming conventions. Open-source Python libraries (Astropy, NumPy, SciPy) will ensure interoperability and reuse in line with FAIR and MSCA best practices.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Any project-specific vocabularies or ontologies will include mappings to standard terms and will be openly published with full documentation in Zenodo or CDS, ensuring they can be reused, refined, or extended.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

Will your data include qualified references^[1] to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[1] A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/13-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Yes. Metadata will include qualified references to original (e.g. FMOS-COSMOS, KMOS/VLT datasets) and other relevant resources (e.g. SERRA simulations, KINMS code), specifying relationships such as 'derived from' or 'used to calibrate,' enabling rich, contextual links for interoperability and reuse.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Comprehensive documentation will be provided, including README files, codebooks, processing workflows, variable definitions, units, and open-source analysis scripts, ensuring that datasets can be validated, understood, and reused in accordance with FAIR and MSCA standards.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All project data will be openly available under CC BY 4.0 and deposited in Zenodo and CDS, with analysis code released under open-source licenses, enabling unrestricted reuse with attribution in compliance with the Grant Agreement.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes. All project data will be deposited in Zenodo and CDS with DOIs, fully documented, and released under open licenses, ensuring long-term usability and reuse by third parties beyond the project lifetime.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Yes. Provenance will be fully documented, including original observations, processing steps, software used, and versioning, following IVOA standards and embedded in metadata and repository records for reproducibility and reuse.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Comprehensive QA will be applied at all stages: raw data validation, processing and reduction checks, verification of derived measurements, inclusion of quality flags, and full documentation, with open-source pipelines to ensure reproducibility and reuse.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Software, workflows, and documentation will be openly released with DOIs. Adequate storage, secure backups, and version control ensure data security. No ethical restrictions apply, as only non-sensitive astronomical data are used. All outputs follow FAIR and MSCA open science principles.

Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Digital outputs such as software, workflows, models, and derived products will be managed via GitHub, Zenodo, and CDS with version control, documentation, and DOIs. No physical materials are produced. All outputs will be FAIR, reproducible, and openly reusable.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Software, workflows, and derived products will be FAIR: deposited in Zenodo/CDS with DOIs, fully documented, openly licensed, interoperable, and accessible via standard protocols. Provenance, versioning, and QA ensure reusability and reproducibility.

Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

Costs for FAIR compliance include personnel time for data curation, documentation, metadata preparation, QA, software management, and secure storage during the short embargo. Long-term archiving in Zenodo and CDS is free, so the main costs are associated with staff effort and institutional support.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

All FAIR-related costs—personnel for curation and documentation, secure storage, and repository deposition—will be covered within the Horizon Europe / MSCA-IF grant, ensuring full compliance with Grant Agreement conditions.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The Principal Investigator (PI) of this project has overall responsibility for data management. Research staff handle data processing, QA, documentation, and software, while institutional IT ensures secure storage. Zenodo and CDS manage long-term preservation and public access.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

All validated datasets, derived products, and software will be preserved long-term in Zenodo and CDS with DOIs. The PI decides what is deposited, based on scientific value and FAIR compliance. Costs are covered by the MSCA-IF grant; long-term preservation ensures reproducibility, reuse, and maximal scientific impact.

Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Data will be securely stored on institutional servers with controlled access, regular backups, version-controlled software, and encrypted transfers. Deposited datasets in Zenodo and CDS benefit from institutional safeguards. No sensitive data are involved.

Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethical or legal issues affect data sharing, as the project only uses non-sensitive astronomical data and openly licensed sources. All sharing complies with Horizon Europe / MSCA open science policies.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No informed consent is needed, as the project does not use personal data. All outputs are non-sensitive and openly sharable in Zenodo and CDS

Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Yes. The project follows Scuola Normale Superiore Pisa data management policies, IVOA astronomy standards, and Horizon Europe / MSCA FAIR/open science guidance, ensuring secure, interoperable, and reusable outputs.